

Automation of Sanatorium Work: Reservation Service and its Structure

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Abstract: This article talks about remote use of services and their advance booking systems in the field of sanatoriums.

Keywords: Booking systems, sanatorium, healthcare, comfortable conditions, innovations.

Introduction: Today, resorts are increasingly thinking about the need to automate their core business processes: dealing with the number and reservation of rooms, planning and accounting for medical services, automating the catering department, etc.

Methods: In general, the sanatorium business is different from ordinary businesses, and it can be called a type of business that combines three: a hotel, a medical institution, a diet restaurant. At this point, the question arises: how to choose a system that provides simple and attractive technical service in sanatoriums, transparent and automatic management of reports, among the most popular and perfect software tools on the world market?

First, we must clearly understand that chaos in a voluntary organization cannot be easily automated. The introduction of the automation system requires a lot of effort to organize the chaos in the sanatorium: to make a detailed map of the number of rooms, to clarify the structure of services, all price lists, to introduce the rules of labor regulations of employees, to work Systematization of travel policy and others.

Second, additional expenses such as purchasing computers (or smartphones for professionals), setting up a network, installing servers, requiring sanatorium staff to learn how to work in the system, and to know how to connect several previously created processes.

Thus, by introducing an automation system, you will get a new business format that all employees of the sanatorium will adapt to. Therefore, any change in the automation system is a laborious and expensive process in many ways, in addition to financial. Thus, choosing an automation system is a very serious process.

When choosing an automation system, it is better to use the following main criteria:

1. If you have several health facilities, they should be automated by one system. Otherwise, there will be difficulties in forming uniform service standards and a common reporting system. It will not be possible to quickly see the status of sanatoriums throughout the network, you will have to manually compile the data yourself. When doctors from different sanatoriums work in different programs, such uneven automation does not allow for sufficient comparison of results.
2. It is very important that the manufacturer has a ready-made online booking module. Then, as soon as the digital (room) fund is automated, you can present yourself as a full-fledged and "advanced" tour operator, providing the agency network and customers with a convenient sales system, without hiring booking managers (using the services of managers).
3. Automation systems for basic business processes (at least in the context of medicine and room management) should be implemented by one developer, and there should be ready and proven integration with other developers' programs (restaurant, accounting, etc.). This saves time, money and nerves during the operation of the system, especially when there is a need for improvement. Anyone who has ever had to connect two different developers will know what I'm talking about.
4. Be sure to ask the developer how long it will take to install the latest version of their product (implementation period). It is important to visit those who have already implemented the system to see how it works in real life.
5. It is absolutely impossible to consider several independent, non-integrated "life" systems of automation in sanatoriums. Instead of making your life easier, it will make your life confusing.
6. Of course, it is better to work with local developers, because you will have to communicate with them for many years with the operation and improvement of the system. Much depends on mutual understanding and efficiency.

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7. Information on how to implement further technical support, version updates, and enhancements should be obtained from the developer.
8. The introduction of the automation system should be under the control of the general director and the sanatorium owner. It is necessary to involve the most professional and strong experts in their field who are responsible for the main business processes in the design and implementation of the implementation.

Results: What can be expected and required from the implementation of the automation system?

Life experience shows that immediately after the introduction of the automation system (if it is implemented correctly, of course), income from both referrals and additional medical services increases in sanatoriums. Of course, the developers cannot guarantee this to you, because a lot will depend on you. If you implement new tools, employees are trained, prepared and motivated, there will be decent results.

Discussion: Strict control over the application of tariffs and the use of rooms and medical services is required by managers and accounting departments.

The system (and you) should see which procedures are included in the price of the tour and which require additional payment.

All computer operations, which are carried out along with the receipt of cash, must be fiscalized, that is, these computer operations must be carried out along with the printing of a fiscal check through the cash register.

Customer service capabilities. For employees, the system will not be convenient at first, and they will communicate this information to you in any way. Of course, the developers need time to prepare a clear technical statement for improving the system.

You, sitting in the office or on a business trip, need to see the current income for any period, the volume of sales, and how many rooms are being renovated, how many guests are planned, which employees are not in line with the current tariffs. did

Your employees will need to throw away a lot of previously used magazines, notebooks and stickers.

Finally, you can add data from different departments. Besides, no one asked about it. Now no one can cheat you (accidentally or on purpose).

Your guests will receive a plan of their procedure at the specific planning office. They do not need to use all sanatoriums to register for treatment. You cancel bills with service Kielce 2023 sh settlements with customers.

Your administrators will see the guest, his preferences, how much money he left in the previous race, what type of guests he saw - VIP-customer or incoming guest - and draw conclusions about how to deal with him.

Instead of closing weekly from working with clients and agents, your reservations department can run a month's worth of reporting with the click of a button.

You will be surprised how much money you spend at the grocery store because they do not have reliable information about the number of visitors and guests.

In short, life will be different. One month later, you can't imagine how the automation system survived before.

Conclusions: Usually, due to the significant low cost of the sanatorium, they decide to develop independently. After all, they suffer with this project for years, continuing to invest money, energy and nerves in it. A self-recording system will never be better and cheaper than the market leaders. Since the sellers of such systems share development costs among their customers and have knowledge of leading industry practices and trends, such products advance the work of various sanatoriums, which are in a competitive environment and the reasons for development are much more than unique endemics.

I would like to emphasize that in this material I express my opinion without claiming its absoluteness. I hope that after reading it, managers of sanatoriums will have an algorithm for the analysis and analysis necessary for choosing an automation system.

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